

Honey Catches more Files than Vinegar: Exploring Secondary Schools Students Craze towards Usage of Information and Communication Technologies for Educational Purposes

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Abstract

Information and Communication Technologies are the essential building-block for technological development. They are gradually penetrating in stakeholders' life to wipe out their digital thirst. Continuous usage of ICT glow students' technological desires and craze in educational institutions. The applications of technologies in educational institutions put far long affect on students' constructive/unconstructive use. Focusing the worth of ICTs in education, the researcher structured current quantitative leading to the positivists' paradigm research to find out students' usage of ICT enrolled in public sector schools of District Lahore of Punjab, on a sample of 1,824 students randomly selected from 10 rural and 10 urban schools where Government of the Punjab established computer labs. After obtaining unfettered and unrestricted permission from the authors, the researcher administered Yusuf and Balogun (2011) scale to collect the data from the respondents. The results of independent samples t-test revealed that male students had more craze usage towards ICT as compared to female students and urban students had better craze towards usage of ICT as compared to female students. The results of and one Way ANOVA ascertained that science students had better usage of ICT as compared to computer science and arts students. On the basis of results, it is recommended that Quaid-i-Azam Academy for Educational Development may arrange female teachers' training working in rural and urban secondary schools using modern digital gadgets and practiced them twice in a week, which may capable teachers to arouse computer science and arts students' craze towards usage of ICT; as ICT is gradually penetrating in every walk of life on the globe.

Introduction

Education is bedrock that stands entire building of individual development. Education is a contributing factor in the improvement of dearth and paucity of societies. It is taking part as an overarching responsibility in every door-step. Education is a milestone for the propagation of technological expansion and intensification. Enhancement in technology is a paramount arbitrator for the development of states (Chan & Elliot, 2004), performing as agent of societal revolution (Watson, 2001), changing nations' living standards and mug the numerical defy for the development of countries (Kiptalam & Rodrigues, 2010). Technology is working as emblematic product (Hassan & Akbar, 2016) and increasing as skyscraping priority of educational institutions (Livingstone, 2003). Innovations are transformed by using contemporary knowledge of contemporary technologies. It is an important to prepare students and youngsters as an innovative and self-assured consumer of use of technology (Steketee, 2005). Usage of copy pencil in educational institutions is going to be eliminated and converted in ICTs formats since last decades (Cortina-Pérez et al., 2014). Some decades observed remarkable climb of ICTs for teaching learning purposes. ICTs put significant effect and bring innovations in promoting students' learning (Ching-Hue & Howard, 2010). Usage of ICT is becoming top priority in educational institutions through developing standards in institutions (Albirini, 2006). ICT makes students skillful and motivates them towards technological innovations (Reynolds et al., 2003), enables students in exchanging, generating and constructing ideas through accumulating, stockpiling and providing chunks of information (Wheeler et al., 2002), arouse students' keen interest and hidden skills (Tondeur et al., 2007), polish their technological potential (Kent & Facer, 2004) and sparkle students' intention towards usage of ICT (McCombs & Ufnar, 2007).

Continuous usage of laptops and computers among students establish momentous and noteworthy effects on their understandings (Cummins et al., 2007). Students used moving pictures, animations, cartoons, illustrating drawings and different software to become more confident using ICT (Kreisel, 2003). They used technology in collaboration of mutual aid and logical solving problems. Students have better craze towards usage of technologies for communication, creation, dissemination, storing and managing information (Crowe,

2006; Grishan & Wolsy, 2011). It develops students' cognitive, innovative, inspired and ingenious thoughts (Graff, 2003; Mikropoulos et al., 2003) and enhances students' concentration and makes them able to reduce their weaknesses for practical life (Anastasiades et al., 2010). Meaningful usage of ICT for students in educational institutions enhances their effective learning, future career opportunities and able them to understand current international standards of innovative technologies (Lau & Yuen, 2013). Students craze towards use ICT for knowledge construction, sharing of ideas, boosts their cognitive development towards understanding, built their creative and imaginative skills in complex circumstances, transformation of innovative ideas towards next generation and for institutional development (Hollandsworth et al., 2011). Future generation is curious and inspired towards understanding and continuous usage of innovative ICT gadgets that provoke their intentions, make them busy in diverse activities and make them effective communicator, information seeker and problems' solvers (Stromquist, 2009). ICT is used for the collection of information, contribution towards empirical evidences, tackling announcement, extending inspirations and exploration of innovative thoughts (Drenoyianni, 2006). Usage of ICT in teaching and learning process acts as a catalyst for students' communal growth, clarity of queries, solution of self-determining responsibilities and investigation of problems (Williams et al., 2012). Students make positive usage of ICT to share their digital learning material. They focus on different search engines for collecting information for their educational and social surviving instead of bookish knowledge, peers' discussion, parents and teachers' experiences (Greenhow et al., 2009; Zakaria et al., 2010). Students who make less use of ICT neither achieve their goals nor make progress in their working life (Richard, 2006).

Applications of ICT among students strengthen their technological skills and able them to defend technological and educational challenges (Plaza-de-la-Hoz & Caro, 2018). Usage of ICT for students makes them effective for resources and goal achievement in daily life. Students' require furnished computer labs and skilled instructors to maximize their skills towards ICT usage (Maharana et al., 2009). Insufficient computers create hurdles in students' understanding (Crawford, 2006). Processing of computer labs with high speed and connected with internet enhance students' learning, make them innovative, realistic, critical thinker and problem solver. Slow speed and scarcity of internet connections make students less skilled and discourage from usage of ICT (Luambano & Nawe, 2004). Nisar et al. (2011) structured quantitative study to find out the use and effect of information and communication technology on randomly selected 429 respondents from Pakistan administering questionnaire having three sub-scales. Findings revealed that 25.7% ICT effects on respondents' educational usage. The results further ascertained significant small correlation between: usage and availability of ICT, usage of ICT and knowledge and usage of ICT and its effectiveness. Yusuf and Balogun (2011) conducted quantitative study to explore practicing teachers' attitudes towards and usage of ICTs on randomly selected 382 respondents, administering self-constructed questionnaire mode of 5-points Likert type options. The findings revealed that practicing teachers have constructive attitudes towards ICT whereas male and female respondents have about same craze towards usage of ICT for educational purposes. Oorkavalan and Arulchelvan (2012) framed a mix-method study to determine the attitudes towards and usage of ICT on learners and educators and its effect on their behaviors during communication on a sample of 490 respondents selected through stratified random sampling techniques in Ana University of India. The data from the teachers were collected through interview protocol and questionnaire was used to collect the data from the students. The results ascertained that teachers were strongly willing and appreciated the usage of ICT for educational purpose as they put constructive affect on upcoming generations and students have deeper craze towards maximum usage of ICT in their educational concerns.

Plethora of literature revealed significant difference among students usage of ICT by students' gender; male students have more access and potential towards maximum usage of ICT as compared to female students. Female students are less interested and make less usage of ICT (Bebetso & Antoniou, 2008). Female students have weak skilled and lose their confidence during usage of ICT. It creates gender differences among students (Jackson et al., 2001; Kadel, 2005). Usage of ICT for educational purpose inspires students' thoughts in both urban and rural areas. There is a lack of scarcity for proper usage of ICT in educational institutions in rural areas (Kadel, 2005; Russell et al., 2004). Rural students are less familiar regarding latest techniques of ICT. It enables students to search books, notes, assignments and other material for their educational needs. Proper usage of ICT either at home or in educational institutions directly effects on both rural and urban students with different educational streams by gender (Saunders & Klemmif, 2003). Rural and urban students show their concentration towards use of ICT in a number of subject areas (Hong et al., 2003). Deficiency of computer facilities in rural schools is due to less Government attention towards allocation of funds for ICT development (Alloway & Dalley-Trim, 2009).

Concern of the current research revolves round students' gender, locality and educational stream. Term *gender* was introduced in the era of 14th century which refers to students group, group of the people or group of inhabitants that vocalized as male, female or sterilize for the purpose of number of communication. Gender is associated with the societal and communal attributes and chances linked with girl, boy and the interactions flanked between male and female. Gender are within societal prepared rules and regulation, set of laws,

attitudes, actions, bustle, characteristic, feature and trait that has been nominated by the community thoughtfulness of logical and sensible recognition for male and female. Distinctiveness, features, uniqueness, individuality and rareness has been created in the society and are educated within the community process. It takes account of group of individuals, race, tribal or national inhabitants and maturity. *Locality* means a place, position, spot, a ward, a region, any area or any section that consist of with or without indication or signals, signs, warnings to happening there. They are being in motion to any other vicinity. The condition or fact that is being local or consists of location: the vicinity that every materialistic thing must possess. By definition urban area means a region, vicinity or locality that is surrounded by the controlled authority and under rules and regulations within the city, municipal firm, company or corporation. It may also be restricted/prohibited place under the jurisdiction of Government, Metropolitans Company, Municipal company, Regime, any Command, Administration or Management (The Punjab Local Government Act, 2019). A rural area is an unlocked and unfasten situation of land that consist of countless quarters, homes, residential places and other constructed materials not for many habitants. It is a common spectrum that rural areas are the geographical areas that are established in remote areas, outside cities and external sides of towns. *Educational stream* means separating students into diverse level clusters that remain together throughout the lesson in educational institutions. It detaches learners based on their educational capabilities into different groups for every one of areas under discussion or assured group of students under preferred set of courses inside the institution. In educational stream, the schools' students are allocate in the course group according to whether students on the whole success is higher than standard, ordinary or lower than standard. The Pakistani schools are offering two educational streams; **Science Stream A:** mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology/computer science and **Humanities Stream B:** general mathematics, general science, education/civics/economics (http://www.biselahore.com/downloads/RTI/Scheme_of_Studies_for_SSC.pdf; Iqbal et al., 2009). In Pakistani public sector schools, mostly market demand subjects are taught and faculty is officially available, whereas parents considered dull, pathetic, absconder and disturbing to those students who opt stream **B** due to low market value and poor money making subject. States/establishment/Institutions officially put away students enrolled in stream **B** from usage of ICT, whereas students enrolled in stream **A** are bound to read, understand and interpret knowledge of ICT under their instructor's guidance (Government of Pakistan, 1998 & 2009). These strong practices only conducted in established computer labs working in public sector schools of the Punjab (Hassan & Akbar, 2016; Hassan et al., 2021; Report on the System of Education in Pakistan, 2006) that enhance students craze towards usage of ICT at local, regional, national and international level. It also brings a positive impact on transforming teaching-learning process from teacher-centered to student-centered.

Statement of the Problem

Relevancy of knowledge and information with use of high demands of technical skills put long lasting effect on individuals' life towards successful career. Usage of ICT is rapidly penetrating in the field of health, business, agriculture, economics and an education as well. It is making change in educational atmosphere, handling and exchanging diversity of information, research, teaching and learning process and so on. It has been considered as one of the imperative sources for the practical and virtuous learning (Anumudu et al., 2018; Baek et al., 2008; Belk, 2013). Convenient usage of ICTs is not so mature in Pakistan (Government of Pakistan, 2001; Hassan & Nawaz, 2021). Since 1980s, the Government of Pakistan took revelatory steps to meet technological demands of the country and to make students more skilled in the field of ICTs and established first computer schooling institute "The Foundation for Advance Science and Technology; *FAST*" in Karachi in 1985 and Lahore 1990s. Lahore University of Management Sciences; *LUMS* gets underway its degree in Computer Science in 1993s. University hired qualified teachers with hi-technologies, scientific, technical and managerial personnel to overcome deficiency of skilled individuals to meet students rising technological necessities (Khan & Shah, 2004). On the other hand, public sector schools working in District Lahore of Punjab of Province are less producing technically literate students. To overcome this deficiency, the government of the Punjab hit a plan, invest billions of rupees, established computer labs, hired skilled and talented staff and furnished labs with modern software and hardware. Punjab Government gives top priority in school education department and establishes computer labs focusing ICTs standards. Establishing of computer labs in public sector educational institutions attract learners' social, cognitive and physical participation and enhances students' enrollment (Hassan & Akbar, 2016). Students' admission necessitates additional computer for convenient usage in schools (Russell et al., 2004). It catches students' mental picture and make them busy on regular basis for educational purposes (Russell et al., 2003). This technical development leaves wide-ranging collisions in education sector. It provides occasions for the learners to take advantage from the current computer labs in their educational path. It reduces students' time, bookish burden and provides new horizons for better learning. Students make maximum usage of ICTs in educational institutions for diversity of purposes (Cortina-Pérvez., 2014; Nisar et al., 2011; Oorkavalan & Arulchelvan, 2012; Plaza-de-la-Hoz & Caro, 2018; Stromquist, 2009; Yusuf & Balogun, 2011; Ziden et al., 2011). Government is showing its poor consent towards schools infrastructural facilities (Saeed & Wain, 2011), qualified teachers (Halai & Durrani, 2017), teachers' poor salaries (Butt et al., 2015), vacant

positions of relevant subject teachers (Hassan & Akbar, 2020; Faize, 2011), poor curriculum and policy (Aubusson & Watson, 1999; Bhatti, 2015; Naq, 2015) and inadequate availability of textbooks (Mahmood, 2010). After facing diverse factors, Pakistani schools teachers are busy in disseminating pedagogical and technological knowledge among students with zeal and zest. On the other hand, technological advancement of states is blasting day-by-day. Students are future mainstay of states and demands billions of rupees to make them technologically literate. The applications of ICT in Pakistani educational institutions are still on trialing pitch (Hassan & Nawaz, 2021). Focusing the worth of ICT, the current quantitative leading to positivist paradigm was framed to explore students' craze towards usage of ICT where Government of the Punjab established computer labs. The researcher is eager to explore male and female students' usage of ICT enrolled in science, arts and computer science streams in rural and urban public sector secondary schools of district Lahore, Punjab-Province of Pakistan.

Research questions

The researcher framed following questions in the current research

1. To compare secondary schools students' craze towards usage of ICT by their gender and locale?
2. Is there any significant difference exist among science, arts and computer science students craze towards usage of ICT?

Research Methodology

Research methodology deals with the method and procedure of study conducted in a logical manner. The current study was descriptive in nature and leads to quantitative research paradigm through conducting survey. Descriptive studies focus on respondents' demographic information by analyzing comprehensive explanation of under study variables (Best & Kahn, 2006). The data is obtained concerning with the current status in account of variables in a condition (Gall et al., 2005). The population of the current research consisted of 57,157 secondary level students; 27,313 male and 29,844 female students of rural and urban public sector secondary schools enrolled in science, arts and, computer science streams. The sample of a study comprised of 1,826 respondents; 765 male and 1,061 female students randomly selected from public sector schools of District Lahore.

After obtaining unfettered and unrestricted permissions from author(s), the author administered *Yusuf and Balogun* (2011) instrument to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire consisted of 35-items based on 5-point Likert type options ranged from strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree used in other studies as well (Edmunds et al., 2012; Hassan & Akbar, 2016; Yusuf & Balogun, 2011). The author piloted initial questionnaire on a sample of 200 participants, which were not included in final data collection. Instrument's reliability was measured by calculating Cronbach's Alpha scores .803. Factor-wise reliability of sub-scales; basic computer operations .742, application software .824, internet resources .866 and use of peripheral ICT equipment was .782 was calculated. The researcher collected the data from respondents ensuring ethical considerations; informed consent, self-respect, well-being, respondents' volunteer participation, assured risk of harm both in physical and psychological as a result of their volunteer participation (Beebe & Smith, 2008; Bull & Lindegger, 2011; Bhutta, 2004; Cohen & Duun, 2011; Jegede, 2009; Kass et al., 2005). Collected data were entered in SPSS for smooth analysis and researcher applied parametric tests. They provide accurate results about respondents' activities (Creswell, 2014; Ivankova et al., 2006), aid researchers to measure the statistical power of respondents' perceptions on measureable constructs (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003) and are performed to obtained reliable results from collected data (Chen & Popovich, 2002; Cohen & Duun, 2011; Johnson & Christensen, 2016; Johnson et al., 2007).

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Data analysis focuses to conquer result and provide clear picture of respondents' perceptions. Following section consists of data analysis and its interpretation. The author analyzes that data in SPSS applying independent sample t-test and one way ANOVA.

Table 1 T-test on students' usage of ICT by gender and locale

Sr.	Variables	N	M	SD	df	t	p
1	Gender						
	Male	766	130.448	19.756	1824	3.94	.01
Female	1060	126.279	23.973				
2	Locale						
	Urban	738	130.243	19.433	1824	3.49	.01
Rural	1088	126.525	24.084				

As ascertained in Table 1, the researcher applied an independent sample t-test to explore students craze towards usage of ICTs by students' gender and locale. The results established significant difference between students' gender; male students have more use of ICT as compare to female students and students' locality; urban students were making more use of ICT as compared to rural students.

Table 2 T-test on factors regarding ICT by students' gender

Sr.	Factors regarding ICT	Gender	N	M	SD	t	p
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1	Basic computer operations	Male	766	33.924	5.350	2.084	.05
		Female	1060	33.367	5.843		
2	Applications software	Male	766	44.514	7.921	4.784	.05
		Female	1060	42.464	9.752		
3	Internet resources	Male	766	44.596	7.935	4.974	.05
		Female	1060	42.464	9.752		
4	ICT equipment	Male	766	15.288	3.055	5.436	.05
		Female	1060	14.428	3.522		

As established in table 2, the researcher used an independent sample t-test to find out usage of ICT by students gender. The results established significant difference between male and female students usage of ICT on factors of basic computer operations, applications software, internet resources and, ICT equipment. It is concluded that male students have more usage ICT on basic computer operations, applications software, internet resources and ICT equipment as compared to female students.

Table 3 T-test for on factors regarding ICT by students' locale

Sr. #	Name of Factors	Locale	N	M	SD	t	p
1	Basic computer operations	Urban	736	33.97	5.34	2.286	.05
		Rural	1090	33.35	5.83		
2	Applications software	Urban	736	44.46	7.64	4.403	.05
		Rural	1089	42.56	9.87		
3	Internet resources	Urban	736	44.54	7.66	4.599	.05
		Rural	1089	42.56	9.87		
4	ICT equipment	Urban	736	15.26	2.85	4.987	.05
		Rural	1090	14.47	3.63		

As ascertained in Table 3, the researcher run an independent sample test was found out students' usage of ICT by students' locality. Results revealed significant difference between male and female students' usage of ICT on factors of basic computer operations, application software, internet resources and, ICT equipment. It is concluded that urban students have more usage of ICT on factors basic computer operations, applications software, internet resources and ICT equipment as compared to rural students' usage of ICT

Table 4 One way ANOVA on students' usage of ICT by educational streams

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Between Groups	9897.939	2	4948.969	9.966	.05
Within Groups	904242.901	1824	496.564		
Total	914140.840	1826			

As presented in Table 4, the researcher applied one way ANOVA to determine students' usage of ICT by students' academic stream. The results declared significant difference between science, arts and computer science students' craze towards usage of ICTs. To explore further, significance difference between science, arts and computer science students' usage of ICT, the researcher applied Tukey post Hoc test.

Table 5 Tukey Post Hoc test on students' usage of ICT by educational streams

Sr. #	Group	N	M	SD	Group	MD	SE	p
1	Science	756	129.96	23.67	Arts	5.51752*	1.27	.05
					Computer science	1.17093	1.25	.35
2	Arts	526	124.45	22.87	Science	-5.51752*	1.27	.05
					Computer science	-4.34659*	1.36	.05
3	Computer science	542	128.79	19.54	Science	-1.17093	1.25	.35
					Arts	4.34659*	1.36	.05

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

As delineated in Table 4, the results of Tukey Post Hoc test reflect significant difference between science and arts students' usage of ICT, no significant difference between science and computer science students and present significant difference between arts and computer science students' usage of ICT.

Table 6 One way ANOVA on factors of students' usage of ICT

Sr. #	Factors	Science		Arts		Computer Science		ANOVA	
		M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	F	p
1	Computer operations	34.10	5.73	32.47	5.96	33.99	5.04	15.098	.05
2	Application software	44.33	9.34	42.14	9.11	43.05	8.52	9.504	.05
3	Internet resources	44.41	9.33	42.15	9.14	43.05	8.52	10.124	.05
4	ICT equipment	15.03	3.30	14.44	3.38	14.78	3.40	4.760	.05

As revealed in Table 6, the results of one way ANOVA declared significant difference between science, arts and computer science students' usage of basic computer operations, application software, internet resources, and ICT equipment. To explore further significant difference, the researcher applied Tukey Post Hoc test.

Table 7 Tukey Post Hoc on factors on usage of ICT by students' educational stream

Sr. #	Factors	p-value	Educational streams					
			Science		Arts		Computer Science	
			Arts	CS	Science	CS	Science	Arts
1	Computer operations		.01	.73	.01	.01	.73	.05
2	Application software		.01	.01	.01	.10	.01	.10
3	Internet resources		.01	.01	.01	.10	.01	.10
4	ICT equipment		.01	.19	.01	.10	.19	.05

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

As ascertained in Table 7, an interpretation of Tukey Post Hoc confirm significant difference between science and arts streams ($p = .01$), no significant difference between science and computer science streams ($p = .73$) and find significant difference between arts and computer science ($p = .01$) against factor students' usage of basic computer operations. Analysis further reports significant difference between science and arts streams ($p = .01$), science and computer science streams ($p = .01$) and finds no significant difference between arts and computer science streams ($p = .10$) in terms of applications software. There exists significant difference between science and arts students ($p = .01$), science and computer science students ($p = .01$) and arts and computer science students ($p = .10$) in account of students' usage of internet resources. There also exist significant difference between science and arts students ($p = .01$), no significant difference between science and computer science students ($p = .19$) and also found no significant difference between arts and computer science students ($p = .10$) towards usage of ICT against factor ICT equipment.

Discussion

The states are paying revolutionary attentions towards spreading information and communication technologies for societal development. An application of technical knowledge, maximum usage of ICTs, discussion with peers, fellows and societal members' urge individual's towards seeking of latest and innovative technological inventions (Stromquist, 2009). The government also focuses on the improvement of individual's skills and for the progress of states. The school is a place where initiatives for development of ICT are taken place. There is considerable less usage of technologies in classrooms that significantly put poor affects on students as well as teachers (Cortina-Pérez et al., 2014; Mullis et al., 2008). The results of current research established significant difference between students' usage of ICT by students' gender, male students have more usage of ICT as compared to female students. Finding of present study consonance with the results of other studies (Cavas et al., 2009; Gillard et al., 2007; Sarfo et al., 2011; Yukhymenko & Brown, 2009; Yusuf & Balogun, 2007; Ziden et al., 2011). Results of current research congruent with the findings of other studies structured in Pakistan which ensures that information and communication technology is becoming essential part of teaching learning process (Batool & Qureshi, 2007), able students' hidden potential towards acquiring better achievements (Hanif, 1999), facilitate students to improve their learning skills (Irum & Munshi, 2015) and arouse students' potential towards better educational intentions (Youssef & Dahmani, 2008; Hassan & Akbar, 2020). Usage of ICT is key construct of students' willingness towards better educational improvement. It fulfills desired expectations of teachers and students during teaching learning process (Cortina-Pérez et al., 2014). Technologies create students learning, high order philosophy of thought and judgment of information in their teaching and learning environment (Khan & Shah, 2004). Latest knowledge of ICT able students to access in renowned educational institutions for higher education (Brennan, 2006; Hassan & Akbar, 2016) and to muddled through ICT global market (Rathod & Jadhav, 2015) that is great shift from traditional to technological based paradigm (Bingimlas, 2009; Mikre, 2012) to facilitate students in educational dimensions (Afshari et al., 2009; Chuang & Rosenbusch, 2005). Findings of present research revealed that female students were lacked in use of application software and use of peripherals ICT equipments and are consisted with the findings of other studies (Hassan & Akbar, 2016; Yusuf & Balogun, 2011). Findings of the current research revealed that urban students have better craze towards usage of ICT as compared to rural students. Urban students have more access on ICT as compared to rural students due to abundance of computer facilities (Harter et al., 2010), reachable technological institutions (Loannides et al., 2008), latest digital gadgets (Hassan et al., 2021), skilled staff (Hassan & Akbar, 2016), availability of electrical appliances (Sanjee, 2015) and vibrant learning environment (Hassan & Akbar, 2020) that arouse students' craze towards usage of ICT.

Availability of T.V. internet libraries, newspapers and NGOs play influential roles in students' attention towards usage of ICT in urban areas. There is scarcity of digital computer labs, poor teaching staff and socio-economic status what abominably affects on rural students usage of ICT (Alston & Kent, 2003; Alloway

& Dalley-Trim, 2009). Students of rural areas have less knowledge of ICT, poor availability of technological gadgets and lack in physical facilities regarding ICT in schools and congruent with the results of other researches (Crawford, 2006; Ndinoshiho, 2010; Swain, 2010). The results of present study established that male students have better usage of ICT as compared to female students which contradict with findings of Sarfo et al. (2011) whose results ascertained no significant difference between students' usage of ICT by gender, due to equal availability of technical gadgets, institutional infrastructure, teachers' training and job securities. There are offered science, arts and computer science streams in public schools of Pakistan (Government of Pakistan, 2002; Iqbal et al., 2009). Students of computer science are taught computer as core subject whereas science and arts students have to use only for their academic purpose. The results of the current research yielded that science students have better usage of ICT as compared to computer science and arts students. It is one of the facts that science and computer science students have more access on video lectures, accent sounds, communicative information and computer graphics (Rajab & Baqain, 2005; Hassan et al., 2021). Science and computer science students have superior usage of ICT in connection with educational related materials that strongly disagrees with the findings of Lindsay and McLaren (2000) that students of arts streams remain dependent on usage of ICT on particular information. The results of the present study support with the findings of study conducted by Ziden et al. (2011) that science students have better usage of ICT. Students of arts stream, have less usage towards ICT as compared to science and computer science students. Applications of teachers digital skills (Liang et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2011), understanding on ICT (Aesaert et al., 2013), attitudes (Kim & Keller, 2011; Wake & Whittingham, 2013) and usage of ICT (Spiteri & Rundgren, 2020; Wastiau et al., 2013) put significant affect on students potential which enhance their craze towards continuous usage of ICT.

Conclusions

Worth of technology is well-known for the human beings since decades. They are basic building block for technological development which are playing catalytic role in penetrating every individual's life to burn technological hunger. They are used at early grades to facilitate students' knowledge, skills and attitudes towards usage of ICT. The core part of educational institutions; teachers put their maximum technological potential in spreading information in the classroom and beyond to enhance students' craze towards better usage of ICT. The author conducted current quantitative leading to positivist paradigm research on a sample of randomly selected 10th grade 1,826 male and female students enrolled in rural and urban public sector secondary schools of District Lahore. The researcher collected the data from the respondents through administering standardized instrument having 35-items mode of 5-point Likert type options. The author piloted initial questionnaire to ensure Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics .803. The results of present study conclude that male students have more use of ICT as compared to female students. They were more craze toward usage of basic computer operations, applications software, internet resources and ICT equipment. They remain in touch with internet libraries and concentrate on part time professional courses for the sake of skills development of ICT. After passing school education, male students have intention to get job as there are more opportunities of jobs for them. Likewise urban students have more craze towards usage of ICT as compared to rural students. Students of urban areas also remain in touch with their teachers/instructors that enhance their interest towards effective usage of ICT. There are more resources and resources of internet, peer-learning, student-teacher relationship and institution that polish urban students entire educational and technological potential in this regards. In urban areas, brands of educational and technological institution catch parents and students concentration through advertising various programs. These programs attract students and polish their technological potential that is poorly available in rural areas. Current research further concludes significant difference between science and arts students, no significant difference between science and computer science students and found significant difference between arts and computer science students against the factors regarding basic computer operations. Science students have more intentions towards usage of ICT. They are eager to make themselves skilled by making computer assignments and tasks in the field of ICT. Students' usage of ICT equipments for understanding of Physics, Chemistry and Biological concepts and diagrams make effective teaching learning process. There was significant difference between science and arts, science and computer science students and found no significant difference between arts and computer science students about usage of ICT against factors regarding application software. Arts students have less intention towards usage of ICT as compared to science students. Arts students remain less skilled and deprived in technological education due to poor understanding, less interest in usage of ICT devices and weak awareness of internet searching. Computer science students were better in usage of ICT among science and arts students. They show their keen interest towards ICT usage and had better understanding of ICT equipments; personal computers, printers and multimedia. Overall study concludes that urban male students have more craze towards usage of ICT as compared to rural female students. Those students who were in computer science and science streams; Physics, Chemistry and Biology, have more usage of ICT as compare to arts students.

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